

EFFECT OF GRAPHENE AND MWCNTs ON MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CFRP

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Ideas and Methods

- Focusing on enhancing the mode I fracture toughness by using two kinds of nano materials, multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and multi-layers graphene, as toughen agent
- MWCNTs and graphene are sprayed on the central two piles interlaminar surface at the same density 1 g/m²
- Analyzing macro and micro fracture appearance to explore the toughening mechanism of two nano materials

Characteristic Curve

SEM Analysis

Conclusion and Discussion

- Toughness of composite laminates shows a remarkable enhancement by adding the MWCNTs and graphene with surface density 1 g/m²
- For composite laminates of mode I fracture, compared with MWCNTs, graphene can greatly enhance its toughness
- Dispersion of experimental data is well explained by the macro fracture appearance

